

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of some Novel Fluorine containing Spiro[3*H*-indole-3,3'-[3*H*]-pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-one Derivatives

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Various substitution reactions, viz. methylation and hydroxymethylation of 2',4'-dihydro-5'-phenylspiro[3*H*-indol-3,3'-[3*H*]pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones (3) have been studied and position of substituents assigned. In all these reactions, substitution occurs preferably at pyrazolyl nitrogen. Further, conversion of the spiro compounds (3) into the corresponding thiones (5) has been carried out. The spiro compounds (3) were synthesised by the reaction of 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-ones (2) with hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol. The compounds have been screened for antibacterial activity. Characterisation of the products has been done on the basis of elemental analyses, ir, pmr and ¹⁹F nmr spectral data.

WE have earlier reported^{1,2} the reaction of 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-ones (2) with different hydrazines in absolute ethanol and glacial acetic acid media yielding various products, viz. 2',4'-dihydro-5'-phenylspiro[3*H*-indol-3,3'-[3*H*]pyrazol]-2(1*H*)-ones, 1,3-dihydro-3-[(2-phenyl-2-hydrazono)ethylidene]-2*H*-indol-2-ones and 1,3-diphenyl-9*H*-pyridazino-[3,4-*b*]indole. It has also been observed that reaction of 2 with hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol gave spiro compounds exclusively in good yields (70–80%). The spiro[indoline-pyrazolins] possess interesting biological activities^{1,3,4}. This system has many reactive sites, viz. indole NH,

pyrazolyl NH, pyrazolyl CH₂ and indole C=O, and we have now studied the methylation and hydroxy-methylation reactions of this system leading to various novel derivatives. Further, since the introduction of thione group is supposed to alter the bioactivity, the spiro derivatives have been converted into the corresponding 2-thiones by an elegant procedure, not reported in such systems earlier.

1,3-Dihydro-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethylidene)-2*H*-indol-2-ones (2) have been synthesised by the Knoevenagel reaction of indole-2,3-diones with acetophenones (Scheme 1). Reaction of an appro-

ropriate indole-2,3-dione with equimolar quantities of required ketone in absolute ethanol in presence of diethylamine resulted in the formation of 1,3-dihydro-3-hydroxy-3-(2-phenyl-2-oxoethyl)-2H-indol-2-one (1; 85–90%), which on dehydration afforded 2 (78–82%). The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral studies.

When 2 reacted with hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol, 2',4'-dihydro-5'-phenylspiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-ones (3) were obtained exclusively. The formation of spiro compounds was confirmed by ir and ^1H nmr spectral data. In ir spectra, characteristic bands were observed at 3350–3150 (NH), 3000–2900 (CH_2), 1700–1680 (C=O) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N). In pmr spectra resonance signals were observed at δ 3.8–4.1 (2H, dd, CH_2), 6.9–7.6 (m, ArH), 8.9 (br, s, NH indole) and 10.1 (s br, NH pyrazole). The spectral data are in agreement with those reported in the literature⁵.

In an attempt to synthesise novel substituted spiro[indoline-pyrazolins], various reactions have been carried out.

When spiro compound 3a ($\text{R}=\text{R}^1=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^2=4\text{-F}$) was subjected to methylation with CH_3I - CH_3COONa , a single product was obtained. The ^1H nmr spectrum of this compound displayed only one methyl signal at δ 2.68 (3H, s, CH_3). In compound 3a, apparently there are three reactive sites for methylation, viz. indole NH and pyrazolyl NH (2'-N) besides pyrazolyl nitrogen (1'-N) which can undergo quaternisation. From the comparison of tlc, m.p.s. and ^1H nmr spectra of the product obtained with 3b ($\text{R}=\text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}^1=\text{H}$, $\text{R}^2=4\text{-F}$), displaying N- CH_3 signal at δ 3.30, it was found that these two compounds are not identical. Further, the physical properties and qualitative test of the compound did not indicate it to be a quaternary salt. On the basis of these observations, it has been concluded that methylation occurs at pyrazolyl nitrogen (2'-N) and 2',4'-dihydro-5'-(4-fluorophenyl)-2'-methylspiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (4a) has been formed.

Further, the reaction of spiro compound 3a with formaldehyde afforded a single product. This product displayed two $-\text{CH}_2-$ signals at δ 3.8–4.05 (2H, dd, CH_2), 4.3–4.45 (2H, dd, CH_2OH) and a broad signal at δ 4.8 (1H, s, CH_2OH). This has confirmed the presence of only one hydroxymethyl group. However, the hydroxymethylation of the spiro compound 3b can give only product with the substitution at pyrazole ring. A comparison of ^1H nmr spectra of these two compounds indicated the same environment of the CH_2OH group. In view of these facts, it appears that hydroxymethylation occurs at 2'-N yielding 2',4'-dihydro-5'-(4-fluorophenyl)-2'-hydroxymethylspiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (4b). Obviously 4c has been formed by the hydroxymethylation of 3b.

Reaction of spiro compound 3 with P_2S_5 in the ratio 1:3 yielded 2',4'-dihydro-5'-phenylspiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-thiones (5) in 78% yield. Formation of thione derivatives 5 has been confirmed in ir spectra by disappearance of C=O absorption at 1720–1670 cm^{-1} and by presence of a sharp band at 1270 cm^{-1} due to C=S. In ^1H nmr spectrum, 4b showed a downfield shift of N- CH_3 protons (δ 3.30–3.78) due to proximity of thioxo group.

The presence and position of fluorine in spiro compounds was confirmed by ^{19}F nmr spectra. Fluorine at 4-position of aryl ring (3a, 3b, 4a–c, 5a, 5b) resonated between δ –111.28 and –112.40 and in compound 3c at δ –115.78 ppm due to the presence of chlorine at *ortho*-position.

Physical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1.

Antibacterial activity: The compounds in ethanolic solution were screened against gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus albus* and gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli* by the Kirby-Bauer method⁶. The Oxford strain of *S. albus* (NCTC 6571) was always kept as control for both the tests. The area of inhibition of growth of bacteria, produced by diffusion of compounds from disc into surrounding medium, was measured. The results obtained are recorded in Table 2.

The results indicate that introduction of alkyl group and fluorine substitution increases antibacterial activity against both types of bacteria. The thione derivatives are good antibacterial agents.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra (TFA+ CDCl_3) on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer (89.5 MHz) using TMS as internal reference and ^{19}F nmr spectra (TFA+ CDCl_3) on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer (84.25 MHz) using hexafluorobenzene as internal standard. Purity of all compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel plates and spots were located either by iodine vapours or uv-lamp. 5-Chloroisatin⁷, 2,5-dichloroacetophenone^{8,9} and 3-chloro-4-fluoroacetophenones¹⁰ were prepared by the reported methods.

1,3-Dihydro-3-hydroxy-3-[2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-2-oxoethyl]-2H-indol-2-one (1c): A mixture of indole-2,3-dione (0.01 mol) and 3-chloro-4-fluoroacetophenone (0.01 mol) and diethylamine (0.5 ml) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 30–60 min¹¹ and then left for 3–4 days. The resulting cream coloured solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (76%), m.p. 204° (Found: N, 4.45. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClFNO}_3$ requires: N, 4.53%).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3-5*

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	R ²	X	Y	M.p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	H	H	4-F	H	O	252 ^a	86	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ FN ₂ O
3b	CH ₃	H	4-F	H	O	229 ^a	88	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O
3c	H	H	3-Cl 4-F	H	O	233	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClFN ₂ O
3d	H	Cl	2,5-diCl	H	O	81	64	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
3e	H	H	H	H	O	201 ^b	76	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O
4a	H	H	4-F	CH ₃	O	122	77	C ₂₇ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O
4b	H	H	4-F	CH ₂ OH	O	191	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₂
4c	CH ₃	H	4-F	CH ₂ OH	O	98	71	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ FN ₂ O ₂
5a	H	H	4-F	H	S	174	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ FN ₂ S
5b	CH ₃	H	4-F	H	S	116	72	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ FN ₂ S
5c	H	H	H	H	S	148	64	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ S

*Compounds 3c, 3d, 4a-c, 5a-c gave satisfactory N and/or S analysis

**Lit. m.p. (°C): ^aRef. 2, ^bRef. 5.

TABLE 2 - ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF COMPOUNDS 3-5*

Compd. no.	R	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Y	Gram (-)	Gram (+)	Standard strain for comparison (NCTC 6571)
3a**	H	H	4-F	H	O	R	R	P.S
3b**	CH ₃	H	4-F	H	O	P.S	P.S.	P.S.
3c	H	H	3 Cl-4-F	H	O	P.S.	R	R
III**	H	F	3-Cl-4-F	H	O	P.S.	P.S.	S
3d**	H	Cl	2,5-diCl	H	O	R	R	P.S.
4a	H	H	4-F	CH ₃	O	P.S.	R	P.S.
IVa**	H	H	4-F	C ₆ H ₅	O	P.S.	P.S.	P.S.
IVb**	H	H	4-F	C ₆ F ₅	O	P.S.	P.S.	P.S.
5a	H	H	4-F	H	S	P.S.	S	P.S.
5b	CH ₃	H	4-F	H	S	S	S	S

*R = Resistant zone, 8 mm ; P.S. = partially sensitive zone, 8-12 mm ; S = sensitive zone, > 12 mm per disc.

**Compounds have earlier been reported by us¹, only antibacterial data given here.

Compound 1d was prepared similarly from 5-chloroindole-2,3-dione and 2,5-dichloroacetophenone, (78%), m.p. 189°.

1,3-Dihydro-3-[2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-2-oxoethylidene]-2H-indol-2-one (2c): A mixture of 1,3-dihydro-3-hydroxy-3-[2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-2-oxoethyl]-2H-indol-2-one (1c; 0.01 mol), concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (16 ml) was heated at 95° on a steam-bath for 30 min¹¹. Ethanol was added to it and then

cooled when orange red needles were obtained (72.5%), m.p. 174° (Found : N, 4.72. C₁₆H₉ClFN₂O₂ requires : N, 4.81%).

Compounds 2d was prepared similarly by the dehydration of 1d, (76%), m.p. 181° (Found : N, 3.89. C₁₆H₈Cl₂NO₂ requires : N, 3.97%).

Compound 1a, 1b, 2a and 2b were earlier been prepared by us² and 1c and 2e are reported in the literature.

2',4'-Dihydro-5'-(3-chloro 4-fluorophenyl)spiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (3c): A mixture of 1,3 dihydro-3-[2-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-2-oxoethylidene]-2H-indol-2-one (2c; 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.012 mol) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 4 h. On cooling, a white solid that separated out was recrystallised from ethanol, (2.26 g, 72%), m.p. 233° (Found: N, 13.34. C₁₆H₁₁ClFN₃O requires: N, 13.31%).

Rest of the spiro compounds were synthesised by following similar procedure.

2',4'-Dihydro-5'-(4-fluorophenyl)-2'-methylspiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (4a): To a methanolic solution of 2',4'-dihydro-5'-(4-fluorophenyl)spiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (3a; 0.002 mol), fused sodium acetate (0.4 g) and methyl iodide (0.002 mol) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 4 h, cooled to room temperature, poured into crushed ice, scratched with a glass rod and kept overnight. The resulting fine colourless solid was recrystallised from benzene, (0.45 g, 77%), m.p. 122° (Found: N, 14.30. C₁₇H₁₄FN₃O requires: N, 14.23%).

2',4'-Dihydro-5'-(4-fluorophenyl)-2'-hydroxymethyl spiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (4b): A mixture of 2',4'-dihydro-5'-(4-fluorophenyl)spiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (3a; 0.005 mol) and formaldehyde (40%; 2 ml) in methanol (30 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 1 h and then cooled to 0° and kept for 12 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from benzene, (1.11 g, 72%), m.p. 191° (Found: N, 13.55. C₁₇H₁₄FN₃O₂ requires: N, 13.50%).

Similarly 4c was synthesised by the hydroxy-methylation of 3b.

2',4'-Dihydro-5'-(4-fluorophenyl)spiro[3H-indol-3,3'-[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-thione (5a): A mixture of 2',4'-dihydro-5'-(4-fluorophenyl)spiro[3H-indol-3,3'-

[3H]pyrazol]-2(1H)-one (3a; 0.01 mol) and phosphorus pentasulphide (0.03 mol) in anhydrous pyridine (40 ml) was refluxed for 18 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The sticky product so obtained was dissolved in 10% NaOH solution and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting solid was recrystallised from benzene, (2.07 g, 70%), m.p. 174° (Found: N, 14.19; S, 10.69. C₁₆H₁₁FN₃S requires: N, 14.14; S, 10.77%).

Similarly 5b and 5c were synthesised.

Characteristic physical and analytical data of all spiro compounds are given in Table 1.

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